

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D6.5

Pathways to develop capacity/skills needs to achieve the Mission targets by 2030

Planned delivery date: 13/05/2025 (M35)

Actual submission date:

Deliverable leader: partner 9 – CETMAR

Authors: Susana Bastón Meira (CETMAR), Lucía Fraga Lago (CETMAR) & Massimiliano Pinat (CNR-IRBIM)

Type of deliverable: Report

Work package Leader: WP6 – CNR

Version: 1.0

Project funded by the European Commission within the HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01	
Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO Confidential, only for member of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

GA No. 101056957 - PREP4BLUE

Start date of the project: June 1st, 2022

www.PREP4BLUE.eu

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DISCLAIMER

“PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters” has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Program call “Preparation for deployment of ‘lighthouse demonstrators’ and solution scale ups and cross-cutting citizen and stakeholder involvement (HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01)”, Grant Agreement n° 101056957.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This document contains information on PREP4BLUE core activities. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation, and publication date. The authors of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the PREP4BLUE Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). “PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters” has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Program call HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01, Grant Agreement n. 101056957.

VERSIONING AND CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Authors (Institution)	Notes
0.1	19.03.2025	Susana Bastón (CETMAR)	First draft prepared by CETMAR
0.2	11.04.2025	Lucía Fraga-Lago (CETMAR)	Review of the document structure & main content
0.3	29.04.2025	Cécile Nys (Ifremer)	Coordination review
0.4	30.04.2025	David Whyte (UCC)	Consortium review
0.5	13.05.2025	Lucía Fraga-Lago (CETMAR)	Revision following on reviews
0.6	14.05.2025	Cécile Nys (Ifremer)	Coordination review
1.0	27.05.2025	Lucía Fraga-Lago (CETMAR)	Final version (to submit)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS.....	6
1 INTRODUCTION: SKILLS NEEDED IN THE BLUE ECONOMY	7
1.1 MISSION RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS	7
1.2 PURPOSE OF THIS REPORT	9
1.3 THE ‘SUSTAINABLE BLUE ECONOMY’ CONCEPT.....	10
1.4 BLUE SKILLS	12
1.5 GREEN SKILLS	13
1.6 DIGITAL SKILLS.....	14
1.7 TRANSVERSAL SKILLS.....	14
1.8 IDENTIFYING GAPS TO BRIDGE IN STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	16
2 PREP4BLUE SKILLS ANALYSIS	18
2.1 INTERVIEWS	19
2.2 FOCUS GROUP	22
3 RECOMMENDATIONS	23
4 CONCLUSIONS	28
5 REFERENCES	29
6 ANNEXES	31
6.1 ANNEX 1: PREP4BLUE QUESTIONNAIRE	31
6.2 ANNEX 2: CHARACTERIZATION OF PREP4BLUE INTERVIEWEES	33
6.3 ANNEX 3: EUROMARINE QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS.....	35

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1. TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS USED IN PREP4BLUE AND THE DOCUMENT	6
TABLE 2. RECOMMENDATIONS ON STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RELATED TO THE MISSION INTERNAL COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	23
TABLE 3. RECOMMENDATIONS ON STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RELATED TO THE MARINE SCIENCE COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	24
TABLE 4. RECOMMENDATIONS ON STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RELATED TO SOCIAL INCLUSION	25
TABLE 5. RECOMMENDATIONS ON STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RELATED TO KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER	26
TABLE 6. RECOMMENDATIONS ON STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RELATED TO CITIZEN AND STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	27

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1: MISSION OCEAN & WATERS ECOSYSTEM. SOURCE: PREP4BLUE PROJECT	7
FIGURE 2: MUTUAL SUPPORTIVE OBJECTIVES. ADAPTED FROM MISSION STARFISH [2]	8
FIGURE 3: OVERVIEW OF THE EU 2030 MISSION RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION ...	9
FIGURE 4: NEXT STEP IN MISSION IMPLEMENTATION. SOURCE: HORIZON EUROPE NCP PORTAL	9
FIGURE 5: TRIPLE HELIX ADAPTATION TO THE MISSION RESTORE OUR OCEANS AND WATERS. THREE MAIN ECOSYSTEMS OF STAKEHOLDERS ARE CONSIDERED BASED ON THEIR DIFFERENT USES OF OCEAN KNOWLEDGE, INDICATED IN RED. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION	16
FIGURE 6: HEXA-HELIX APPROACH TO THE USE OF OCEAN KNOWLEDGE BY THE DIFFERENT GROUPS OF STAKEHOLDERS; DETAILS OF THE MAIN TYPE OF STAKEHOLDERS IN EACH GROUP ARE INDICATED IN THE SIDES OF THE FIGURE. THE RED TITLES IDENTIFY THE MAIN INTERESTS DRIVING THE RELATION OF EACH ECOSYSTEM WITH OCEAN KNOWLEDGE. SPIRALS REPRESENT THE GAPS THAT SHOULD BE BRIDGED TO TRANSFER OCEAN KNOWLEDGE THROUGH ALL THE LAYERS OF THE SYSTEM. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION	17
FIGURE 7: RECOMMENDED LADDER OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACCORDING TO EXPECTATIONS FOR PARTICIPATION. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION	18
FIGURE 8: INPUTS AND END-USERS OF THIS REPORT. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION	19
FIGURE 9: LIVE RANKING OF SKILLS FOR THE MISSION SUCCESS AT THE EMB STEERING COMMITTEE. SOURCE: SLIDO	20
FIGURE 10: IDENTIFICATION OF MOST RELEVANT TYPES OF SKILLS. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION	20
FIGURE 11: SUGGESTED SKILLS. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION	21
FIGURE 12: CLASSIFICATION OF TYPE OF ACTIONS. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION	21
FIGURE 13: FIVE MISSION OVERARCHING OBJECTIVES FOR 2030. SOURCE: AUTHORS ADAPTION FROM MISSION STARFISH 2030 [2]	31
FIGURE 14: RESPONDENT'S ROLE	33
FIGURE 15: NUMBER OF ANSWERS PER TYPE OF ORGANIZATION	33
FIGURE 16: GENDER	33
FIGURE 17: YEARS OF EXPERIENCE	33
FIGURE 18: COUNTRIES	34
FIGURE 19: ANSWERS PER EVENT	34

Executive Summary

PREP4BLUE is a €4.9 million, three-year project framed within the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”. This document outlines strategies to build the capacities and skills needed to meet the Mission’s ambitious objectives by 2030, particularly in preparing stakeholders and citizens during the Mission’s first phase (2022–2025).

The main objective of this report is to explore what kind of skills are needed to boost citizen and stakeholder engagement in Mission Ocean & Waters, supporting major changes for protecting and restoring the ocean and rivers and making the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular. It brings together knowledge and ideas from all PREP4BLUE Work Packages, focusing on the needs of researchers, policy-makers, industry actors, and citizens. By identifying shared challenges and opportunities, the report provides a set of recommendations to help different groups work better together and develop the knowledge, tools, and strategies needed to achieve the Mission’s goals.

The identification of key skill needs was done through interviews, webinars, focus groups, and stakeholder consultations. **Transversal skills** (e.g., communication, stakeholder engagement, co-design) were consistently ranked as most essential, followed by technical and digital skills. Actions to **scale and replicate solutions**, and those fostering **citizen engagement**, were seen as most critical for the Mission's success.

A set of 19 key recommendations are structured into five groups:

1. **Communication & Awareness:** Centralize information across projects, create multimedia materials, and clarify social media roles.
2. **Social Inclusion:** Promote participation of underrepresented groups (ethnic minorities, persons with disabilities, LGBTQIA+), and use inclusion KPIs.
3. **Knowledge Transfer:** Develop training for under-resourced regions, implement monitoring, and support science diplomacy.
4. **Citizen & Stakeholder Engagement:** Engage stakeholders early, tailor incentives, foster long-term feedback loops, and support grassroots initiatives.
5. **Ocean Literacy:** Boost training and citizen involvement through programs like EU4Ocean and online resources.

The report emphasizes that achieving the Mission’s goals requires **inclusive, well-coordinated, and capacity-driven engagement** at all levels — from policy and research to citizen action.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in PREP4BLUE and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
P4B	PREP4BLUE
DOA	Description of the Action
CEDEFOP	European Centre for Development of Vocational Training
CSA(s)	Coordination and Support Action project(s)
CSO	Civil Society Organization
EC	European Commission
ECOP	Early Career Ocean Professionals
EMB	European Marine Board
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, and Occupations
GIS	Geographical Information System
HEA	Higher Education Authority
KPI	Key Progress Indicators
KTOSM	Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module
LLL	Lifelong Learning
MIP	Marine Implementation Platform
(the) Mission	Mission 'Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030' / Mission Ocean & Waters
MSC	Marine Science Communication
MU	Multi-use
NGO(s)	Non-Governmental Organization(s)
NW	Northwest
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OL	Ocean Literacy
OTGA	Ocean Teacher Global Academy
R&I	Research and Innovation
RTOs	Research and Technology Organizations
SEO	Search engine optimization
VET	Vocational and Education Training

1 Introduction: Skills needed in the blue economy

1.1 Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters

Missions are a novel instrument in Horizon Europe, with the aim of tackling societal challenges with systemic solutions. The implementation of five thematic missions by 2030 (Restore our Ocean and Waters; Adaptation to Climate Change; Cancer; Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities; Soil Health and Food) was launched in 2021 by a [Commission Communication on European Missions](#). The objective of the Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030' is to provide a systemic approach for the restoration of our ocean, seas and waters by 2030.

The Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters (hereafter 'the Mission') is implemented in two phases: a first "development and piloting" phase (2021-2025), followed by a second "deployment and upscaling" phase (2026-2030). During the first phase, the Mission rolled out 'Lighthouses' in major European sea and river basins, as the Mission sites: the Atlantic & Arctic Sea basin ([BlueMissionAA](#)¹), Baltic & North Sea ([BlueMissionBANOS](#)²), Danube river and Black Sea ([EcoDaLLI](#)³) and Mediterranean Sea ([BlueMissionMed](#)⁴) [1]. Figure 1 shows the Mission Ocean & Waters Ecosystem.

Figure 1: Mission Ocean & Waters Ecosystem. Source: PREP4BLUE project

The Mission has three specific objectives, listed below (Figure 2):

1. Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity (in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030)
2. Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters (in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil)

¹ <https://bluemotionaa.eu/>

² <https://bluemotionbanos.eu/>

³ <https://ecodalli.eu/>

⁴ <https://bluemotionmed.eu/>

3. Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular (in line with the European Climate Law and the holistic vision supported by the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy)

Figure 2: Mutual supportive objectives. Adapted from Mission Starfish [2]

Figure 2 shows how the three main objectives are mutually supportive. The core is to regenerate ecosystems by directly protecting and revitalising them. This already major task will not be complete unless pollution is halted. But as climate change is intimately linked to the health of the Ocean, the transition to climate neutrality by decarbonising the blue economy is also essential.

The Mission has also to be driven through two transversal enablers (Figure 3):

- Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System
- Public mobilization & engagement.

Piloting deep transformation also requires bridging the major gaps in science, observation and forecasting capacity that still exist in the EU and globally. The goal is to build on the existing forecast and climate modelling infrastructures and services (including [Copernicus services](#) for marine, climate, coastal, emergency, inland waters, etc.) and pool together all available observation data, first at EU-level then globally, into an open-source, easily accessible and understandable interface and matching application and an interactive platform: a **Digital Ocean and Waters Knowledge System** (enabler 1).

Reaching the ambitious targets set for this Mission will not be possible without the full support of people and science. Empowering citizens to better value and safeguard their ocean and waters is a key enabling intervention to underpin major economic and social transformations; for this reason, **public mobilization & engagement** has been considered as the enabler 2. All channels should be used: education of all generations, citizen voluntary engagement such as beach clean-up initiatives, citizen science, and ocean-literacy initiatives for the public at large.

Mission Oceans & Waters is a collaborative effort at the EU, national, regional, and local levels. The assessment of EU missions showed they are timely and inspiring, align with EU policy priorities, and encourage **stakeholder engagement**. However, they need more political support, improved governance, better access to resources and knowledge, and increased citizen and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 3: Overview of the EU 2030 Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters. Source: Authors' elaboration

1.2 Purpose of this report

This work supports the next steps of the Mission implementation (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**) by identifying a relevant set of skills and capabilities needed to help achieve o the Mission's goals by 2030.

Figure 4: Next step in Mission Implementation. Source: [Horizon Europe NCP portal](https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-05/ocean_water_intro.pdf)⁵

⁵ https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-05/ocean_water_intro.pdf

This report is a legacy document that contributes directly to the objectives of the Mission, particularly focusing on *Enabler 2 – Public mobilisation and engagement*. It explores the types of skills and knowledge needed to strengthen citizen and stakeholder involvement in the Mission. Drawing from insights developed across all PREP4BLUE activities, the report addresses the needs of researchers, policy-makers, industry actors, and citizens. By identifying shared challenges and opportunities, the report aims to help different groups work better together and develop the knowledge, tools, and strategies needed to achieve the Mission’s goals.

The report also provides targeted recommendations to support the involvement with the Mission of three key groups—(a) the research and innovation community, (b) policy and funding stakeholders, and (c) citizen, societal representatives and sectoral stakeholders —through the lens of public mobilisation and engagement⁶.

1.3 The ‘sustainable blue economy’ concept

On the blue economy’s labour market, the [green transition](#) is already giving rise to job vacancies: In the offshore wind energy sector alone, the number of jobs could triple by 2030; but this increase is accompanied by a demand of new skills - up to 30% of offshore renewable energy companies, for instance, complain either that the skills they need are unavailable or there are shortages in existing skills (*e.g.*, technicians)[3, p. 240]. Making the transition from ‘blue growth’ to a ‘sustainable blue economy’ the European Commission (EC) put efforts on the following aspects:

- Encourage and facilitate the creation of skills partnerships under the [Pacts for Skills](#) in the industrial ecosystems relevant for the blue economy as identified in the [EU Industrial Strategy](#) (such as in offshore renewable energy or shipbuilding); Recently [the Union of Skills](#) was created, aiming to reduce skills and labor shortages across Europe, with a particular focus on the sciences, technology, engineering and math (STEM) and information and communication technology (ICT) fields.
- Launch in 2022, under the European Maritime, Aquaculture and Fisheries Fund, a new call for proposals on **blue careers** and a specific call for proposals on women aiming at **increasing women’s representation** in the workforce and raising their profile in the formal governance of the blue economy.
- [Report on the implementation of the EU Directive on Maritime Spatial Planning](#) in 2022 [4], following the adoption of national maritime spatial plans in March 2021, and prepare proposals on how the EC can facilitate cross-border cooperation and encourage Member States to integrate objectives of offshore renewable energy development in their national spatial plans.
- Promote maritime spatial planning internationally through **cooperation** with the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (**IOC**) of **UNESCO**.
- The [EU4Ocean Coalition](#), an initiative recently set up by the EC, brings together diverse organisations, projects, and individuals dedicated to promoting **ocean literacy** and sustainable ocean management.

⁶ The PREP4BLUE proposal considered jointly the policy makers and sectoral stakeholders; the present report has reorganized these groups for the recommendations, based on the use of ocean knowledge by different stakeholders groups, as presented in section 1.8, figures 5 and 6.

- The EC also cooperate with the [Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO \(IOC-UNESCO\)](#), Member States and international partners to contribute to the **ocean literacy programme of the UN Decade of Ocean Science** for Sustainable Development 2021-2030.
- Promote and support, through EU funds, the development of **marine and coastal eco-tourism**. EU support will aim to showcase the diverse maritime heritage of the continent, manage tourist flows smartly, diversify the offer and extend off-season tourism.
- Continue to **support outermost regions**, in line with its 2017 Communication [5], in seizing the opportunities offered by their large exclusive economic zones, in protecting their exceptionally diverse ecosystems, in developing their own sustainable **blue economy strategies** and in exchanging best practices to address their common **climate adaptation challenges**.
- Continue to invest in a special relationship with neighbourhood and enlargement countries to **develop blue economy supply chains** that enhance links with the EU.
- Support multilateral initiatives such as the [UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration](#) and the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030 [6], in particular on **ocean observation, ocean modelling and data sharing infrastructure**.
- Update its **international ocean governance agenda** in the light of recent consultations and recommendations by the [International Ocean Governance Forum](#) [7]. The agenda should ensure that the blue economy protects and does not harm the marine ecosystem; it should promote **transparent and inclusive decision-making and raise social sustainability standards**. In line with this, the [European Ocean Pact](#) is being set up, with the aim of bringing coherence across all EU policy areas linked to oceans. Focusing also on supporting resilient and healthy oceans and coastal areas, promoting the blue economy.

There is an urgent need to rethink and optimize the use of ocean space. However, there is growing concern that the ocean space is being developed for single use (an area solely used by one business activity); efficiencies in space use and synergies could be created by applying a more holistic approach. Developing an area to accommodate several business activities (“multiuse” or “MU”), making more efficient use of the ocean is part of the solution, as resources in close geographic proximity are shared, representing a shift away from exclusive resource rights. MU requires a specific governance structure as different stakeholder interests need to be aligned to create synergies, reduce risk and avoid conflict. [8]

The Commission aims to reach out to all maritime stakeholders to engage with them in shaping a sustainable blue economy in a fair and equitable way [3]

1.4 Blue skills

In March 2025 was published the “*Study to support and design skills development in the blue economy*” [9], in which it can be found a first draft definition for blue skills: “**Blue skills are a comprehensive set of knowledge, values, attitudes, competencies, and qualifications that one should acquire to live in, develop and support the sustainable development of the blue economy**”. This definition is orientated to all blue economy sectors, including R&I. This definition was firstly released in 2024, during the mentioned study, and for this reason, in many documents that fed this report, the term employed to identify blue skills has been technical skills (for Mission Ocean & Waters)

The blue economy’s research and innovation sector requires a diverse array of blue skills that integrate scientific expertise, technological proficiency, and interdisciplinary collaboration. Today’s core demands span traditional fields such as marine biology, oceanography, environmental science, and engineering, while increasingly emphasising advanced competencies in data science, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), machine learning, and remote sensing technologies. [9]

The maritime sector indicates that skills such as robotics, data management, digital literacy, environmental monitoring, and collaborative research are key. Several reports from bodies such as the [European Marine Board](#) (on marine graduate training) and [EuroGOOS](#) (on ocean literacy) make clear that addressing skill shortages requires not just more technical training but also enhanced soft skills, multi-stakeholder engagement techniques, and environmental awareness. This is corroborated by the European Council’s recommendation on key competences for lifelong learning (LLL) [10], ESCO’s inclusion of a set of transversal skills on its standardised skill taxonomy, and OECD analyses of the evolving labour market [11].

Advancing ocean science is fundamental to understanding and addressing marine challenges. The [UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development \(2021-2030\)](#) emphasizes the need to bolster global ocean science capabilities, particularly in developing countries, to ensure equitable access to knowledge and technologies. Horizon Europe underpins several missions and thematic calls, including Mission Ocean & Waters. These initiatives support projects that monitor, protect, and restore marine ecosystems. They enhance scientific understanding through improved marine observation networks and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) data systems, directly feeding into evidence-based policymaking and the broader objectives of the [European Green Deal](#).

Also the [EU Digital Decade](#), and policies such as the European Skills Agenda, the EU’s Digital Strategy and the European Green Deal all highlight the need for sector employees to develop transferable digital, technical and management skills [9]

The European Commission’s Expert Group on the skills and career development in the blue economy has identified three key areas of importance for their discussions: a) education-industry cooperation, b) ocean literacy and c) lifelong learning (LLL), mobility, education programs. [12]

The European Commission supported in 2023 the [European Year of Skills](#) which's main objectives were

- Reduce skills gap between education offer and labour market needs.
- Improve communication and cooperation between education and industry.
- Improve the attractiveness and awareness of career opportunities in the blue economy.
- Improve the ocean literacy culture at the basis of it all.

From now on until 2030, Marine Science Communication (MSC) has become critical to achieve a more ocean literate and sustainable society. The publication “Future Science Brief 8” of the European Marine Board [13] identified nine recommendations to strengthen the capacity of MSC in Europe. These MSC recommendation are quite aligned with the ones of the present report, because communication is key for stakeholder engagement.

1.5 Green skills

Although the term *green skills* is more established than the *blue skills*, there is still a debate in the literature on whether it is relevant or not to talk about *green skills* [11]. [Cedefop](#) (2013) [14] defines green skills as “*the knowledge, abilities, values and attitudes needed to live in, develop and support a sustainable and resource-efficient society*”, however other studies defend that skills cannot be green *per se*; that they are the competence and abilities that individuals possess (such as finger dexterity, oral communication, repairing skills) that are used to carry out tasks that contribute to a greener economy.

[OECD](#) and Cedefop (2014) [15] define green skills as “*the skills needed by the workforce, in all sectors and at all levels, in order to help the adaptation of products, services and processes to the transformations due to climate change and to environmental requirements and regulations*”.

What seems to be clear is that there is a growing demand for green skills in several sectors: addressing the energy transition, green engineering techniques, increased circularity, compliance with environmental regulations, and more generally a better understanding of how the blue economy sectors interact with the environment.

Considering the importance to support the [Green Deal](#), there is an increasing interest in Europe to understand and promote the skills, competences and attitudes supporting sustainable practices, commonly identified under the tag of green skills. In fact, one of the the policy actions set out in the European Green Deal as a catalyst to promote learning on environmental sustainability in the European Union has been the development of a European sustainability competence framework. Commonly identified as GreenComp [16] identifies a set of sustainability competences to feed into education programmes to help learners develop knowledge, skills and attitudes that promote ways to think, plan and act with empathy, responsibility, and care for our planet and for public health.

For this reason, the present report has addressed green skills needs separately from the set of blue skills, even in some cases they may be very related.

1.6 Digital skills

Digital skills — sometimes referred to as digital literacy, digital competence, ICT-related skills, or e-skills — are essential for navigating today's technology-driven society. While these terms are often used interchangeably, they cover a wide spectrum of competencies, ranging from basic abilities to use digital tools to highly advanced technical and cognitive capabilities.

In general terms, digital skills encompass both the technical know-how required to operate digital technologies and the broader cognitive, emotional, and social skills necessary for their effective and responsible use. Digital competence extends beyond technical proficiency, incorporating knowledge, critical thinking, and attitudes related to the ethical, legal, and reflective use of digital information and technologies in everyday life [17].

The European Union has provided several foundational definitions in this field. In its 2006 Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning, the European Parliament and the Council defined digital competence as the confident and critical use of Information Society Technology (IST) for work, leisure, learning, and communication, supported by basic ICT skills like accessing, managing, and exchanging digital information.

More recently, in 2022, the European Commission's Digital Competence Framework ([DigComp](#) [18]) offers a comprehensive understanding of digital competence. It includes the ability to search, evaluate, and manage digital information; to use tools for communication, collaboration, and content creation; and to apply digital technologies in ways that support critical thinking, creativity, and innovation.

For the purposes of this report, the term digital skills is used in a broad and inclusive way, aligned with the EU's DigComp framework. This terminology is more widely recognised in everyday language while still encompassing the depth and scope of digital competence.

Given the centrality of digital transformation to the EU's strategic goals⁷, digital skills have been analysed as a distinct category in this research. They are essential for ensuring technological sovereignty, bridging the digital divide, and promoting an inclusive and human-centred digital environment. The EU's [Path to the Digital Decade Policy Programme](#) underscores this importance, setting ambitious targets: ensuring that 80% of adults attain at least basic digital skills and reaching 20 million employed ICT specialists by 2030.

In light of these priorities, identifying gaps in digital skills and understanding their role in Mission Ocean & Waters is crucial to ensuring successful engagement, innovation, and implementation across stakeholder communities.

1.7 Transversal skills

Transversal skills — also commonly referred to as *soft skills*, *key competences*, or *basic skills* depending on the classification framework — are fundamental to personal and professional development. While terminology may vary, these skills are universally recognised for their value across all sectors, job types, and stages of life and learning.

⁷ Digital skills most relevant policies, flagship initiatives and instruments can be consulted at <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-skills>

The [European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations \(ESCO\)](#) taxonomy formally began integrating transversal skills in 2020. ESCO defines them as *transversal knowledge, skills and competences* that are broadly relevant across occupations and economic sectors. They serve as the foundation upon which more technical or sector-specific (“hard”) skills are built, and are essential for individuals to successfully adapt and thrive in the labour market.

According to ESCO, transversal skills and competences can be grouped into six main categories:

1. Core skills and competences
2. Thinking skills and competences
3. Self-management skills and competences
4. Social and communication skills and competences
5. Physical and manual skills and competences
6. Life skills and competences

The [European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training \(CEDEFOP\)](#) defines transversal skills as *learned and proven abilities commonly seen as necessary or valuable for effective action in virtually any kind of work, learning, or life activity*. These skills are not confined to any one context — such as a job, sector, or discipline — and are distinct from, though closely related to, transferable skills. They are also often referred to as *non-cognitive, socio-emotional, or core skills*, though these terms may describe narrower subsets of the broader category.

Transversal skills are gaining increasing attention at the EU policy level. In connection with the **2023 European Year of Skills**, the European Commission launched a dedicated web section⁸ recognising their critical role in shaping inclusive and resilient societies. These skills — including **critical thinking, teamwork, communication, adaptability, and learning to learn** — are viewed as vital for effective engagement in work, education, and everyday life. They also play a key role in supporting sustainable economic growth, fostering social inclusion, and boosting EU competitiveness.

In the context of a rapidly changing labour market, marked by the twin green and digital transitions, transversal skills are becoming more important than ever:

- **14%** of current jobs are considered highly automatable.
- **32%** of jobs are expected to change substantially due to AI and automation this decade.
- A significant **24.5%** of candidates are reported to lack adequate transversal skills.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) across the EU are especially sensitive to these shifts. When asked about future skill priorities, **68%** of SMEs identified soft skills as increasingly important, followed by **62%** for digital skills and **42%** for green skills.

In light of these developments, this report treats transversal skills as a distinct and critical category.

Given their overarching importance, **transversal skills have been presented as a distinct category in the questionnaires used throughout our research**. This decision reflects their central role not only in fostering effective **stakeholder engagement**, but also in enabling **communication** and **knowledge transfer**—three pillars essential to the success of the Mission

⁸ Transversal skills section on the European Union website, developed during the 2023-2024 European year of skills https://year-of-skills.europa.eu/transversal-skills_en

Ocean & Waters. The capacity to collaborate across disciplines, communicate with diverse audiences, and adapt to evolving challenges depends strongly on the presence of these skills. Their cross-cutting nature makes them especially relevant to the Mission Ocean & Waters context, where collaboration, adaptability, innovation, and effective communication are indispensable to fostering systemic and transformative change.

1.8 Identifying gaps to bridge in stakeholder engagement

Within the PREP4BLUE project, the main groups of stakeholders and their interests in relation to ocean knowledge were identified. Although the penta-helix model was employed for the stakeholders characterisation, for the purpose of this report a **triple helix approach** was proposed (Figure 5), based on the use of ocean knowledge by different stakeholders groups. Our interest is to identify the gaps in the transfer of ocean knowledge across the three ecosystems, in order to propose recommendations for bridging them.

Government main interest in ocean knowledge is to develop policies and manage funding. The knowledge ecosystem main interest is, obtaining data and information and providing trainings to transfer them, and finally the socio-economical ecosystem, is interested in getting solutions and solving needs based on the ocean knowledge. There are bilateral interactions between the three ecosystems to support an Ocean Knowledge-Based Economic Development.

Figure 5: Triple helix adaptation to the Mission Restore Our Oceans and Waters. Three main ecosystems of stakeholders are considered based on their different uses of ocean knowledge, indicated in red. Source: Authors' elaboration

If we zoom into those three ecosystems (Figure 6) and we search for the detail of the groups of stakeholders composing them, a subdivision in one can be done, obtaining an hexa-helix approach. Therefore, in the governance group, we can differentiate between the decision makers, which include policy makers, marine protected areas managers, standardization bodies, etc. from the funding organizations that would include think tanks in Marine Science and other funding organizations.

Figure 6: Hexa-helix approach to the use of ocean knowledge by the different groups of stakeholders; details of the main type of stakeholders in each group are indicated in the sides of the figure. The red titles identify the main interests driving the relation of each ecosystem with ocean knowledge. Spirals represent the gaps that should be bridged to transfer ocean knowledge through all the layers of the system. Source: Authors' elaboration

The knowledge ecosystem include in one hand knowledge owners, which refer to research and technology organizations (RTOs) and universities and in the other hand knowledge providers: schools and vocational education training (VET) centres, media, ocean literacy networks. Some organizations may take part from both of those subgroups, like universities that provide training and develop research. In this analysis we have classified them on what we have considered their primary activity in relation to ocean knowledge.

Regarding the socio economical ecosystem, it can be split in business and industry, *i.e.*, companies, industrial clusters, business developers, entrepreneurs, *etc.* from citizen and citizen and civil society organizations (CSOs).

All these groups need to relate among them to have access and contribute to the ocean knowledge. There are some relationships that may be more natural or easier to develop as those within each subgroup. But there is also a need to bridge the gaps between the three main ecosystems. This is represented by the spirals because at the end, there are many ways of interrelation, and all the groups should have some kind of facilities to transfer knowledge and capacities and to disseminate ocean knowledge through all the layers of the system. The recommendations proposed in this report address the gaps identified in figure 6, represented by the spirals.

To complete this analysis, within PREP4BLUE an adaptation of the Arnstein' ladder [19] was done, following the Portfolio Analysis **EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030"** [20]. As indicated in Figure 7 sensibilization actions imply a lower level of maturation in engagement, stakeholder engagement is needed for co-creation and co-implementation of actions, and when there is an urgency for solutions collaboration with local and regional authorities is recommended.

Figure 7: Recommended ladder of stakeholder engagement according to expectations for participation. Source: Authors' elaboration

2 PREP4BLUE skills analysis

The main objective of PREP4BLUE was to set the foundations for co-creating and co-complementing the research and innovation required to achieve Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030. With that purpose citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies were analysed and tested as well as business models and knowledge transfer related with the Mission Ocean & Waters objectives.

Figure 8 is based on five different data sources:

- a) Face to face interviews held during high-level meetings in 2024;
- b) Webinars on Citizen and Stakeholder engagement;
- c) Stakeholder assemblies;
- d) A focus group to identify skills needs in the Mission Ocean & Waters framework;
- e) Desktop analysis/Literature review.

Both interviews and webinars focused on general skills for the success of Mission Ocean & Waters: the interviews gave us the possibility to identify the perception that different groups of stakeholders had in relation to skills needs for the Mission success, while the webinars identified good practices in all sea basins. Complementing this approach, the focus group targeted **skills needs** with emphasis on **key obstacles and enablers for stakeholder engagement** that directly impact the implementation of the Mission' solutions. The aim was to collect information from all PREP4BLUE work packages to identify the recommendations arising from each of them.

Figure 8: Inputs and end-users of this report. Source: Authors' elaboration

2.1 Interviews

In October 2023, the PREP4BLUE team undertook 56 interviews at a series of high-level events related to the Mission Ocean held in the vicinity of Galicia (NW of Spain):

1. The [EurOcean Conference](#) held in Vigo;
2. The [European Marine Board](#) (EMB) steering committee annual meeting held in Vigo;
3. [EMB ECOP \(Early Career Ocean Professionals\) Network Forum](#) held in Santiago de Compostela;
4. 10th Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference ([ASPC 2023](#)) held in Porto;
5. plus 14 attendees at the [EuroMarine network](#) steering committee meeting, who answered over an online platform.

The aim of this work was to make a qualitative pre-identification of the main capacities and skills required to achieve the goals of the Mission, integrating the views of a balanced group of stakeholders. These five events allowed to interview different profiles (senior & junior researcher, policy-maker and industry stakeholders), reaching a balanced group in terms of age, gender, and years of experience.

Figure 9 shows that the thirteen attendees to the EMB steering committee identified that **the most relevant skills** for the success of the Mission Ocean & Waters are: in first place transversal skills, second position technical skills, followed by green skills and lastly digital skills.

To succeed on this type of action, what kind of skills or capacities do you consider more crucial?
(Please rate the following skills from 1 - more important to 4-less important)

Figure 9: Live ranking of skills for the Mission success at the EMB steering committee. Source: Slido

This is consistent with the total of answers collected from the rest of events (Figure 10) in which transversal skills were identified as the most relevant, followed by technical skills and leaving digital and green skills as less relevant.

Figure 10: Identification of most relevant types of skills. Source: Authors' elaboration

When asked about specific skills related to Mission Ocean & Waters, Communication and Stakeholder engagement were identified in first place, followed by Ocean Literacy, Multidisciplinary skills, Marine science, Policy/Law, Empathy and Scientific knowledge (Figure 11). Please note that these were open-ended responses, they were not suggested in advanced to the interviewees.

Figure 11: Suggested skills. Source: Authors' elaboration

The questionnaire also addressed the five types of pledges that can be proposed by stakeholders to support the Mission, due to their relation to specific sets of skills, necessary to develop each type of pledge. Interviewees were asked to rank the two types of pledges they found most critical in terms to achieve the Mission's goals (or rephrased otherwise, those that would critically hamper the achievement of the Mission's goals if they are not achieved with the desired level of success).

As shown in figure 11, respondents considered crucial for the success of Mission Ocean & Waters to undertake actions to upscale, deploy and replicate solutions (32% ranked first). This result proofs interviewees' awareness of the Mission, which states that the development and piloting phase (2021-2025), will be followed by a deployment and upscaling phase (2026-2030), where the solutions piloted in the first phase will be **developed, replicated and scaled up**, enabling broad implementation and participation in the Mission across the EU and its bordering basins [21]. Citizen engagement, outreach and awareness raising was chosen as the second type of pledge crucial for the Mission success (39% ranked second).

Figure 12: Classification of type of actions. Source: Authors' elaboration

Skills identified by respondents

Skills identified by respondents as important for the success of the Mission Ocean and Waters were Communication, Stakeholder engagement, Ocean Literacy, multidisciplinary skills, marine science, policy/law, empathy and scientific knowledge.

2.2 Focus group

A focus group was organized to jointly analyse the main lessons learnt from PREP4BLUE's activity, considering the main tasks and events developed. In particular, the Stakeholder Assemblies were of special relevance for this debate, as those events gathered an important number of inputs from a diverse group of stakeholders. They covered the four Lighthouse areas, and were adapted to the specific needs and formats identified in each case, mobilising 400 stakeholders in the process. The pilot assemblies provided a tangible framework for stakeholder engagement, testing and validating relevant engagement methods and event formats that will guide future engagement strategies within the Mission Ocean & Waters. All details can be found in the [D6.3 Report on the findings of the stakeholder assembly's engagement pilots](#).

All work package leaders were requested to reflect on the barriers encountered when engaging stakeholders and the recommendation they could provide us to solve that barrier. A specific template was developed for this purpose. Then, a focus group session was organized on 21st February 2025 where the authors of this report discussed the main recommendations on stakeholder engagement that come out of the project from their different perspectives:

1. Management
2. Communication
3. Citizen engagement
4. Knowledge transfer
5. Business planning
6. Stakeholder engagement

The discussion focused on skills relevant to transformative changes in the blue economy. All PREP4BLUE work packages promoted and enhanced collaboration with various organizations to facilitate think-tank activities and gather data from stakeholders. Therefore, the aim of the focus group was to leverage insights from project activities to create tailored recommendations for engaging stakeholders effectively.

The results of this process are the set of recommendations presented in section 3 of this report.

3 Recommendations

Based on the analysis of PREP4BLUE activities, the following key recommendations are proposed to strengthen stakeholder engagement and citizen participation in the Mission Ocean & Waters (Tables 2 to 6).

Table 2. Recommendations on Stakeholder engagement related to the Mission Internal communication activities.

Group	Recommendation	Stakeholders			Description
		R&I	Policy-makers & Funding organisations	Citizens CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders	
	Centralize information and opportunities		✓		Establish a unified platform that consolidates information from the 60 Mission Ocean & Waters projects, making it easier for citizens and stakeholders to access updates, funding opportunities, and engagement activities without navigating multiple websites. Skills: Web developer skills, SEO
	Consolidate information on funding opportunities		✓		Create a centralized platform that aggregates funding opportunities from various projects, simplifying access for stakeholders and reducing the need to navigate multiple sources. Skills: Web developer skills, SEO
	Clarify social media responsibilities and compliance		✓		Clearly define roles and responsibilities for managing social media channels, ensuring compliance with EU regulations. Address any legal ambiguities proactively to maintain a consistent and effective online presence. Skills: Project management

Table 3. Recommendations on Stakeholder engagement related to the marine science communication activities.

Group	Recommendation	Stakeholders			Description
		R&I	Policy-makers & Funding organisations	Citizens CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders	
<p>Marine Science Communication (MSC)</p>	Establish dedicated mixed teams to manage communication for specific initiatives like the Mission Ocean & Waters.	✓	✓	✓	<p>Dedicated communication groups that include project partners and representatives from the EC. These teams should be supported by clear guidelines, key messages, and consistent terminology tailored for social media use, to ensure coherent and effective outreach within the broader institutional communication framework.</p> <p>Skills: communication, social media knowledge</p>
	Plan and execute high-impact public engagement events	✓	✓		<p>Allocate sufficient resources and time to organize events that genuinely engage the public and extend beyond the immediate project community. Large-scale, well-promoted events can significantly raise awareness and foster broader participation.</p> <p>Skills: organizational skills, effective communication, financial skills, logistics</p>
	Develop diverse narratives	✓	✓		<p>Crafting multiple narratives tailored to various cultural and ethnic groups ensures broader reach and resonance, particularly among marginalized communities.</p> <p>Skills: cultural awareness, communication</p>
	Develop engaging multimedia content			✓	<p>Produce documentaries and videos showcasing mission activities, covering the four Lighthouses because they address different problems and show cultural diversity, and make them available in multiple languages with subtitles. This approach can inspire and inform a broader audience about the mission's objectives and progress.</p> <p>Skills: videomaking, storytelling, project management</p>

Table 4. Recommendations on Stakeholder engagement related to social inclusion.

Group	Recommendation	Stakeholders			Recommendation
		R&I	Policy-makers & Funding organisations	Citizens CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders	
 Social inclusion	Ensure that co-creation and stakeholder engagement processes are designed with cultural sensitivity in mind	✓	✓		<p>This includes recognizing and addressing power imbalances, respecting diverse cultural identities, and adapting engagement approaches to suit the specific needs and contexts of different stakeholder groups</p> <p>Skills: co-design, facilitation methods</p>
	Strengthen diversity and inclusion strategies within Mission activities	✓	✓	✓	<p>By building on existing efforts in gender and youth inclusion, dedicated actions to promote the participation and visibility of ethnic minorities, persons with disabilities, and LGBTQIA+ individuals. Develop inclusive guidelines and monitoring mechanisms to ensure equitable representation and meaningful roles across all dimensions of diversity in research and innovation initiatives.</p> <p>Skills: social inclusion, empathy</p>
	R&I calls might stipulate the use of gender, equality diversity and social inclusion key progress indicators (GEDSI KPIs) to monitor progress	✓	✓		<p>Achievement of standard indicators for the quality of the inclusion, <i>i.e.</i> how to collect evidence of social inclusion</p> <p>Skills: Impact monitoring, social inclusion monitoring</p>

Table 5. Recommendations on Stakeholder engagement related to knowledge transfer.

Group	Recommendation	Stakeholders			Recommendation
		R&I	Policy-makers & Funding organisations	Citizens CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders	
<p>Knowledge transfer</p>	Promote knowledge sharing of successful regional strategies	✓	✓		<p>Highlight and disseminate successful examples of regions aligning their strategies with Mission Ocean & Waters objectives, such as those involving smart specialization strategies. Sharing these practices can guide other regions in adopting similar approaches. Some examples may be the Mission Forum, Mission Arenas, Mission transversal working group...</p> <p>Skills: Communication, stakeholder engagement</p>
	Develop and deliver targeted capacity-building programmes	✓	✓	✓	<p>Continue promoting tailored training courses or workshops focused on EU funding instruments, application processes and knowledge transfer methodologies and how to enhance project impact. These should be specifically designed for under-resourced regions and less-experienced stakeholders, to ensure more equitable access to funding opportunities aligned with Mission Ocean & Waters objectives.</p> <p>Skills: proposal writing, contribution to knowledge transfer processes</p>
	Implement continuous evaluation and adaptation	✓	✓		<p>Regularly assess the effectiveness of knowledge sharing activities and be prepared to adapt strategies as needed. This includes gathering feedback from stakeholders and define impact indicators.</p> <p>Skills: Designing KPIs, monitoring KPIs</p>
	Promote and support participation in structured training on European Science Diplomacy	✓	✓		<p>Including certified modular courses, to build capacity among scientists, policymakers, and diplomats. This will enhance their ability to collaborate effectively, align with EU global engagement priorities, and apply science-based approaches to international policy and cooperation, e.g., Science Diplomacy Course</p> <p>Skills: Science diplomacy</p>

Table 6. Recommendations on Stakeholder engagement related to citizen and stakeholder engagement.

Group	Recommendation	Stakeholders			Recommendation
		R&I	Policy-makers & Funding organisations	Citizens CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders	
<p>Citizen & Stakeholder engagement</p>	Customize communication strategies	✓	✓		Adapt communication methods to effectively engage different stakeholder groups, considering their unique contexts and preferences. Skills: storytelling
	Involve stakeholders early	✓	✓		Engage stakeholders from the inception of projects or policies to ensure their feedback is integrated throughout the development process Skills: contribution to co-design processes
	Foster public-private-research collaborations	✓	✓		Encourage collaborations among public authorities, private businesses, and research institutions to drive innovation and address challenges related to Mission Ocean & Waters objectives. Skills: collaboration
	Provide tangible incentives for engagement		✓	✓	Offer clear benefits for public participation, such as travel and accommodation grants to attend the Mission Forum or competitions for mentorship visits with business or research leaders Skills: develop funding schemas, identify funding needs
	Foster long-term engagement through structured feedback and decision-making integration	✓	✓	✓	Create permanent stakeholder advisory committees for sustained engagement and develop feedback loops where stakeholders can track how R&I inputs influences decisions. Skills: promote knowledge transfer, contribute to knowledge transfer processes

4 Conclusions

This report brings together insights from a range of activities carried out across the PREP4BLUE project to identify the skills and capacities needed to achieve the objectives of the Mission Ocean & Waters. The analysis is based on multiple sources, including interviews, stakeholder assemblies, webinars, a focus group, and a review of relevant literature. Together, these inputs provided a well-rounded view of stakeholder perspectives, skill gaps, and engagement practices across different sea basins.

The interviews conducted during high-level events in 2023 revealed that transversal skills — such as communication, stakeholder engagement, and multidisciplinary collaboration — are considered most essential for Mission success. Technical skills were also valued, while digital and green skills appeared less prominent in responses. Open-ended feedback highlighted communication, stakeholder engagement, ocean literacy, and empathy as key skill areas.

Participants in the interviews also identified the most critical types of actions needed to meet Mission goals. The top priorities were: scaling and replicating solutions, followed by engaging citizens and raising awareness.

Webinars and stakeholder assemblies added further insights, demonstrating how effective engagement practices — from co-creation to citizen science — can be adapted to local contexts and scaled up. The assemblies, held in the four Lighthouse regions, engaged over 400 participants and helped test participatory models in real settings.

To consolidate these findings, a focus group involving leaders from across the project's activities reflected on common barriers to engagement and proposed practical recommendations. These discussions led to a set of 19 actionable recommendations, grouped into five groups:

1. **Communication & Awareness:** Centralize information across projects, create multimedia materials, and clarify social media roles.
2. **Social Inclusion:** Promote participation of underrepresented groups (ethnic minorities, persons with disabilities, LGBTQIA+), and use inclusion KPIs.
3. **Knowledge Transfer:** Develop training for under-resourced regions, implement monitoring, and support science diplomacy.
4. **Citizen & Stakeholder Engagement:** Engage stakeholders early, tailor incentives, foster long-term feedback loops, and support grassroots initiatives.
5. **Ocean Literacy:** Boost training and citizen involvement through programs like EU4Ocean and online resources.

In summary, advancing the Mission requires building inclusive, well-supported, and cross-sectoral collaboration frameworks. Skills development and stakeholder engagement are not peripheral — they are central enablers of the transformative change the Mission seeks to achieve by 2030.

5 References

- [1] D. E. Kampa *et al.*, ‘Baseline Study for the Implementation of Lighthouses of the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”’, Publications Office of the European Union, Report, Sep. 2022. doi: [10.2777/34856](https://doi.org/10.2777/34856).
- [2] Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) *et al.*, *Mission Starfish 2030: restore our ocean and waters*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2020. Accessed: Feb. 05, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/70828>
- [3] *COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS on a new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU Transforming the EU’s Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future*. 2021. Accessed: Mar. 18, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:240:FIN>
- [4] European Commission, ‘Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council outlining the progress made in implementing Directive 2014/89/EU establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning, COM(2022) 185 final, Brussels’, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52022DC0185>
- [5] European Commission, ‘COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE, THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS AND THE EUROPEAN INVESTMENT BANK A stronger and renewed strategic partnership with the EU’s outermost regions {SWD(2017) 349 final}’, 2017. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex:52017DC0623>
- [6] UNESCO, IOC, and DG Research & Innovation, ‘Roadmap for Cooperation on the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030)’, Apr. 2024. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/2e5f29fb-cb0c-4d0d-8840-97ce0ee9730c_en
- [7] J. Dodgshun *et al.*, ‘EU International Ocean Governance Forum. Setting the course for a sustainable blue planet: Recommendations for enhancing EU Action.’, 2021. Available: <https://3rd-iog-forum.fresh-thoughts.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/89/2021/04/IoG-recommendations-2021-WEB.pdf>
- [8] E. Scholten and R. van Steennis, ‘Maripark Blueprint’, EY Advisory Netherlands LLP, ED none 155-01-0649, 2024. Available: <https://www.noordzeeloket.nl/publish/pages/230658/ey-adviesrapport-blueprint-maripark-online-version.pdf>
- [9] Cappell, R., Cavaliere, F., Kesicka, A., Fraga, L., Irawan Rincón Y., Soto A., L., Chever, T., Herry, L., Potier, ‘Study to support and design skills development in the blue economy Literature Review’, *Publications Office of the European Union*, 2025. Available: https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/document/39cca58b-eaab-4f88-a40d-a4dc858c94d5_en
- [10] European Commission, *Council Recommendation of 20 December 2012 on the validation of non-formal and informal learning*. p. 5. Available: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=oj:JOC_2012_398_R_0001_01
- [11] OECD, *Assessing and Anticipating Skills for the Green Transition: Unlocking Talent for a Sustainable Future*. in *Getting Skills Right*. OECD, 2023. doi: [10.1787/28fa0bb5-en](https://doi.org/10.1787/28fa0bb5-en).

- [12] M. Vinx *et al.*, 'Training the 21st Century Marine Professional: A new vision for marine graduate education and training programmes in Europe.', Ostend, Belgium, Apr. 2018. doi: [10.31230/osf.io/n3ms9](https://doi.org/10.31230/osf.io/n3ms9)
- [13] J. Seys *et al.*, 'Marine Science Communication in Europe: A Way Forward', Jun. 08, 2022, *Zenodo*. doi: [10.5281/ZENODO.6444143](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6444143).
- [14] 'Skills for a low carbon Europe: the role of VET in a sustainable energy scenario | CEDEFOP'. Accessed: Mar. 19, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/events/skills-low-carbon-europe-role-vet-sustainable-energy-scenario>
- [15] OECD and European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training, 'Greener Skills and Jobs', OECD, Feb. 2014. doi: [10.1787/9789264208704-en](https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264208704-en).
- [16] G. Bianchi, U. Pisiotis, and M. Cabrera, *GreenComp: the European sustainability competence framework*. in JRC science for policy report, no. 30955. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2022. doi: [10.2760/13286](https://doi.org/10.2760/13286).
- [17] European Parliament. Directorate General for Parliamentary Research Services., *Digital skills in the EU labour market: in depth analysis*. LU: Publications Office, 2016. Accessed: May 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2861/451320>
- [18] R. Vuorikari, S. Kluzer, and Y. Punie, *DigComp 2.2 - the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens: with new examples of knowledge, skills and attitudes*. in EUR, no. 31006. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2022. doi: [10.2760/115376](https://doi.org/10.2760/115376).
- [19] S. R. Arnstein, 'A Ladder Of Citizen Participation', *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 216–224, Jul. 1969, doi: [10.1080/01944366908977225](https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225).
- [20] European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., *Portfolio analysis, EU mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030": analysis of a portfolio of projects financed by sixteen EU programmes contributing to the objectives and enablers of the mission ocean and waters*. LU: Publications Office, 2023. Accessed: Dec. 09, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>
- [21] Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (European Commission) *et al.*, *Restore our ocean and waters: a synergy info pack by CORDIS*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2022. Accessed: Feb. 05, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex 1: PREP4BLUE questionnaire

1. Among the five arms of the Mission Restore Our Oceans and Waters, which one do you resonate most with? (Tick the chosen one)

Figure 13: Five Mission overarching objectives for 2030. Source: Authors adaption from Mission Starfish 2030 [2]

2. The mission ocean is gathering pledges for action from all stakeholders. **In your opinion, which of the following types of action are more challenging for achieving the Mission' objectives?** Please rank the two types of actions that you find most critical in terms of their potential impact on the mission's goals if they do not achieve the desired level of success.

- Research and innovation
- Actions to gather and share Evidence-based knowledge and data
- Actions to upscale, deploy and replicate solutions
- Action for citizen engagement, outreach and awareness raising
- Education and training

3. To succeed on this type of action, what kind of skills or capacities do you consider most crucial? *(Please rate the following skills from 1-more important to 4-less important)*

- Technical skills addressing the goals of the Mission, (i.e. Marine Ecology, Climate Change Risk Management, Aquatic ecosystems, Marine pollution)

Type of skill/STH addressed

- Digital skills (i.e. modelling/ digital twins / GIS, ICT)

Type of skill/STH addressed:

- Green skills (i.e. renewable energies, circular economy, SDGs, EVs)

Type of skill/STH addressed:

- Transversal skills (i.e. innovation management, stakeholder engagement)

Type of skill/STH addressed:

6.2 Annex 2: Characterization of PREP4BLUE interviewees

Respondents were mainly from Research and Academia (63%), but also from industry (33%).

Figure 14: Respondent's role

Figure 15: Number of answers per type of organization

Respondents were gender-balanced and covered from early-researchers & students to experienced professionals (33% have less than 5 years of experience, 35% more than 15 and 33% just in between).

Figure 16: Gender

Figure 17: Years of experience

Atlantic coastal communities were the best represented with a clear majority of Spanish people, but including people from 15 different countries.

Figure 18: Countries

The distribution of responses by Event explains the even distribution of years of experience since the ECOP meet Early Career Ocean Professionals and the EurOcean provide a forum for the marine and maritime research community and wider stakeholders to interface with European and Member State policymakers and strategic planners.

Figure 19: Answers per Event

6.3 Annex 3: Euromarine questionnaire results

Please rank the two types of action you find more challenging for achieving the Mission' objectives 14

To succeed on this type of action, what kind of skills or capacities do you consider most crucial? (Please rate the following skills from 1-more important to 4-less important) 13

Could you describe with a maximum of 2 keywords the type of skills you deem more necessary?

